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**CO-CONTINUOUS CALCIUM PHOSPHATE/POLYCAPROLACTONE COMPOSITE BONE SCAFFOLDS
FABRICATED BY DIGITAL LIGHT PROCESSING AND POLYMER MELT SUCTION**

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4 **Abstract**
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7 Innovative scaffolds consisting of a cartesian mesh of interpenetrated composite struts of polycaprolactone
8 (PCL) and β -tricalcium phosphate (β -TCP) in a core/shell configuration are developed. Photocurable slurries
9 with high solid-loading (40 vol.% TCP) and reduced viscosity were produced by adding camphor and used to
10 fabricate ceramic preforms with hollow struts through Digital Light Processing (DLP). After sintering the
11 structures were suction-infiltrated by molten PCL, resulting in co-continuous composite scaffolds. Their
12 mechanical performance was evaluated in compressive and bending tests and analysed under the light of
13 stress fields calculated by finite element numerical simulations. Toughness of the scaffolds was notably
14 increased after incorporating the polymeric core. The new co-continuous architecture facilitates impregnation
15 and improves the isotropy of the reinforcement provided by the polymeric core over other reported
16 alternatives but increases the stresses in the ceramic. This was compensated, however, by the increased
17 intrinsic strength associated to using a more concentrated feedstock.
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32 **Keywords:** composite materials; ceramic; polymer; mechanical properties; digital light processing; computer
33 simulations.
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4 **1. Introduction**
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6 Artificial implants are today undeniably necessary to repair bone lesions and restore its normal function due
7 the limitations of the current gold standard solution for bone healing: autografts, and the also commonly used
8 allografts [1,2], that seem not always adequate for load bearing or large defects [3,4]. The demand of artificial
9 implants is especially accused in elderly population but not limited to it, and the number of replacement
10 surgeries to substitute loose implants is increasing. Indeed, younger patients may require multiple such
11 surgical interventions as the average joint implant lifetime is estimated to be in the 10-15 years range, not to
12 mention the cases where implants replacements are needed in order to adapt to body changes.
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21 To solve the mentioned limitations, it is today acknowledged that an alternative capable of adapting to the
22 defect and actively induce bone reconstruction needs to be found. Indeed, there are numerous studies focused
23 on the development of bioactive scaffolds, porous structures capable of aiding the natural healing process and
24 enable the regeneration of critical defects. These scaffolds have to meet several requirements in order to fulfil
25 its regenerative function: they must consist of biodegradable and osteoconductive materials, and have an
26 interconnected porosity to serve as substrate and vehicle for cell proliferation and tissue ingrowth [3,4].
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34 Several bioceramic materials (calcium phosphates, sulphates, bioglasses and glass-ceramics) meet the cited
35 requirements, as they promote bone regeneration and can be degraded during the process [2,5]. Scaffolds
36 fabricated from such materials by traditional manufacturing techniques have shown promising bone
37 regeneration capabilities both in vitro and in vivo [6], but their mechanical performance is still far from that of
38 natural bone tissue [4]. And even though a high mechanical performance seems not to be essential in certain
39 applications, avoiding stresses in regions of the skeleton subjected to load is not possible. In those cases, the
40 use of external metallic fixation is inevitable at least until the regeneration is well underway and the scaffold
41 plus the newly formed tissue can stand the loads on their own. Poor mechanical performance can also
42 complicate the handling of the scaffolds by the surgeon during implantation. The improvement of the
43 mechanical behaviour of such osteoregenerative scaffolds is therefore a priority for them to become a valid
44 alternative to traditional metallic implants in clinical orthopaedic applications for regions of the skeleton
45 subjected to any significant stresses.
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4 Unlike traditional fabrication methods, additive manufacturing (direct ink writing, stereolithography, selective
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6 later sintering, etc.) allows the fabrication of bioceramic structures with highly interconnected pores at
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8 reduced total volumetric porosity, thanks to a controlled architecture, which significantly increases their
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10 mechanical strength [3,7]. Nevertheless, improving their deficient toughness is also essential to cope with the
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12 demanding mechanical environment of many orthopaedic applications. To this end, a polymeric
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14 biodegradable phase is often added to the 3D-printed bioceramic scaffold. The most widespread strategy
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16 consists in coating the external surface of the bioceramic by impregnation [8–12]. However, recent studies
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18 have sought to preserve the bioactive surface of the ceramic's exposure to the surrounding tissue and fluids by
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20 introducing the polymer on internal channels within the scaffolds' struts. Such core/shell hybrid scaffolds
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22 [13–16] are, thus, expected to have better biological performance both *in vitro* and, especially, *in vivo* thanks
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24 to the osteoconductive nature of the bioceramics [17].
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28 However, up to now the core/shell strut scaffolds resembled those fabricated by coaxial extrusion where the
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30 polymer is not interconnected neither within each deposited layer nor with adjacent layers. An increased
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32 interconnectivity of the polymeric phase is deemed beneficial to enhance the mechanical integrity of the
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34 scaffolds under more complex loads and will yield a more isotropic mechanical behaviour of the hybrid
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36 structure. Consequently, this study is concerned with the fabrication by DLP of innovative hybrid scaffolds
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38 with fully interconnected polymeric cores, as shown in Figure 1. Thus, scaffolds with interpenetrated hollow
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40 struts were fabricated using newly-developed, high-solid-loading suspensions of β -tricalcium phosphate (β -
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42 TCP) powder in photosensitive resins and subsequently molten polycaprolactone (PCL) was infiltrated into
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44 their internal channels by suction. PCL is a ductile polyester, widely used in the replacement of hard tissues
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46 [18] that in previous works was proved to provide excellent toughening of bioceramics scaffolds when fully
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48 impregnating the structure or even applied as a simple coating [9,19,20]. Degradation time of PCL is typically
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50 quite long, which is adequate to preserve mechanical performance during the whole process of bone healing
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52 but will produce the insulation of the bioceramic surface from the biological medium for an extended period
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54 of time, significantly retarding the biodegradation of the whole scaffold [21].
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58 The resulting structures were microstructurally and mechanically characterized by means of both compression
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60 and bending tests, to analyze the improvement of strength and toughness upon polymer infiltration compared
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4 to bare ceramic structures. The mechanical characterization of additive manufactured ceramic and hybrid
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6 scaffolds under compressive stresses is frequently found in the literature, but studies analyzing their flexural
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8 behaviour are more limited, especially in the case of hybrid scaffolds manufactured by Digital Light
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10 Processing (DLP). The present study seeks, thus, to redress this deficiency given that bending is the most
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12 deleterious loading mode to which bone implants are exposed.
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15 **2. Materials and methods**

16 **2.1. Fabrication and microstructural characterization**

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21 Three-dimensional models of the scaffolds were constructed with a CAD software (Creo Parametric 6.0, PTC
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23 Corporation). The model consisted of 7 layers of interpenetrated cylindrical struts either hollow (Fig. 2) or
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25 dense. Model dimensions, as displayed in Fig. 2b, were selected to match as closely as possible those of
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27 scaffolds fabricated in previous studies [14]: the distance between struts in the horizontal and vertical planes
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29 were $s = 2.35$ mm and $h = 1.92$ mm; and the external strut diameter was $d = 1.32$ mm, both for dense and
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31 hollow structures while the internal diameter of the latter was $d_i = 0.62$ mm. Two appendages were added at
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33 both ends of the scaffold model (Fig. 2c) to serve as inlet (and outlet) for the polymer into the internal
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35 channels of the struts, which are interconnected throughout the structure in all directions (Fig. 2b).
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38 To obtain photo-sensitive suspensions with a 40 vol. % of ceramic content, the materials conforming the
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40 liquid and solid phase were preconditioned. A commercial unpigmented acrylic resin (FTD Standard Blend
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42 3D Printing resin, Fun to Do, Alkmaar, The Netherlands) with 1.130 g/cm³ and a viscosity of 0.07 Pa·s (at a
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44 shear rate of 10 s⁻¹) formed the basis of the liquid phase of the suspensions. In order to reduce its starting
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46 viscosity a 30 wt.% of camphor was added [22]. On the other hand, the β -TCP powder (Whitlockite OD,
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48 Plasma Biototal Limited) with 2.36 μ m of average particle size and 3.07 g/cm³ of density was coated with a
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50 0.1 wt.% of oleic acid (OA) in order to avoid sedimentation [23,24]. Higher concentrations of OA entailed an
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52 undesired viscosity increase in the final suspension. Once prepared, elements were mixed in a centrifugal
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54 planetary mixer (ARE-250, THINKY Corp., Japan) to ensure its homogeneity, thus creating suspensions with
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56 a 40 vol. % of ceramic content. To further reduce their viscosity, the suspensions were kept at a temperature
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58 of 40 °C during the whole printing process. The resin and the ceramic powder exhibit similar refraction
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60 indexes: 1.5 and 1.63 respectively [25,26]. The suspension was loaded in a transparent vat installed in the
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4 DLP equipment (Asiga Max Mini UV385, Asiga, Australia). This printer uses a UV LED projector with a
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6 wavelength of 385 nm and a light intensity of 31 mW/cm². To obtain a scaffold, the UV-light projector
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8 consecutively displays images corresponding to each of the 25 μm layers in which the corresponding CAD
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10 model was sliced for an exposure time of 0.132 s to cure the resin. The system uses a bottom-up fabrication,
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12 where parts stand attached on the printing base which moves vertically away from the vat's bottom every time
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14 a layer is exposed to allow the suspension to flow underneath the printed part, and then back towards the vat's
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16 bottom for printing the next layer. After the printing was finished the part was post-processed. First, uncured
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18 suspension remnants occupying the macropores of the scaffolds were removed using isopropanol and
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20 sonication, and the internal channels of the struts were cleaned by injecting isopropanol with a syringe. Parts
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22 were then minimally exposed to compressed air to eliminate the last traces of solvent or uncured resin.
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24 Cleaned samples were then post cured in a UV-light chamber to ensure full polymerization for a safe handling
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26 of the specimens.
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30 Considering the result of the thermogravimetric analysis performed on the green bodies (Figure 3), debinding
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32 of the samples was performed through a two-stage treatment at 334 °C and 390 °C, for 2 hours at each
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34 temperature, with a slow heating rate of 0.5 °C/min in all ramps, to avoid any deformation or microcracking
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36 on the printed parts, while ensuring the complete elimination of the acrylic resin. Parts were then sintered at
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38 1200 °C for 2 hours, using a heating rate of 3 °C/min to reach that temperature, followed by free cooling after
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40 the treatment. Once sintered, selected samples were impregnated with polycaprolactone. The PCL (Capa
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42 6500, Perstorp Holding AB, $M_w = 50000$ Da) was molten at 180 °C to infiltrate by suction the internal
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44 channels of the struts: one of the sample lateral appendages (Fig. 2c) was immersed in the PCL melt while
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46 vacuum was applied at the opposite end.
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49 The variations in the part dimensions with respect to the CAD file, due to light scattering from TCP particles,
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51 as well as the shrinkage suffered after the different post-treatments, were evaluated by scanning electron
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53 microscope (S3600 N, Hitachi, Japan). Fabricated parts were subsequently cut into scaffold specimens
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55 without appendages prior to their mechanical characterization. The apparent density of each specimen was
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57 estimated from its weight and external dimensions, measured using a digital balance and a caliper.
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2.2. Mechanical characterization

The compressive strength (σ_c) of scaffolds with dense, hollow and hybrid struts was determined from the maximum load registered during uniaxial compression tests. For each type of sample, a minimum of 10 cubic specimens of around 5 mm side were compressed either perpendicularly (\perp) or parallel (\parallel) to the building plane on a universal testing machine (Shimadzu Autograph AG-IS), at a constant crosshead speed of 0.6 mm/min. Flexural strength (σ_f) of the fabricated structures was estimated by conducting three-point bending tests in a minimum of 7 specimens (per type of sample) with external dimensions of approximately $5 \times 5 \times 25$ mm. In these tests the load was applied in the direction perpendicular (\perp) to the printing plane at a constant crosshead speed of 6 mm/min. The maximum loads (F_{\max}) registered in the tests were used to calculate the σ_f using the following equation:

$$\sigma_f = \frac{3 L F_{\max}}{2 w t^2}$$

where L is the distance between the support cylinders and w and t are the specimen's width and thickness, respectively.

To evaluate the toughness improvement achieved upon polymer infiltration, strain energy densities (G) of scaffolds with dense, hollow and hybrid struts were compared. These values were calculated as the area under load-displacement curves divided by the volume of the tested sample. In particular, the area was evaluated up to maximum strains of 0.4 ($G_{0.4}$) in the case of compression tests and a displacement of 4 mm (G_4) in bending, considering the distance between supports (20 mm) as the relevant length to estimate the sample volume.

2.3. Numerical modelling

Models of interpenetrated struts scaffolds and analogous log-pile structures with feature dimensions similar to those of the experimental specimens were employed to perform finite elements simulations in ABAQUS/Standard software (Dassault Systemes Simulia Corp., Providence, RI), with the aim of analyzing the stress fields developed under compressive stresses. An isotropic elastic behaviour was assumed for the materials, with the following elastic properties: $E = 65$ GPa, $\nu = 0.28$ for β -TCP [27] and $E = 0.53$ GPa and $\nu = 0.47$ GPa [28] for the PCL polymer. The FEM grid consisted of tetrahedral quadratic elements with improved stress formulation (C3D10I) with elements ranging from a maximum size of 200 μm down to ~ 20 μm at the surface of a representative central cell that was partitioned to increase stress accuracy while keeping

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4 the computational time reasonable. Fixed boundary conditions were imposed at the bottom surface of the
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6 scaffold, while a 0.1 mm displacement was applied on the top surface to simulate a uniaxial compression test.
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10 11 **3. Results and Discussion** 12

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14 The first objective of this study was to improve the solid content on the resin suspensions over previous works
15 [29], in order to enhance the mechanical performance of the DLP scaffolds. Thus, the solid content was
16 increased from the roughly 27 vol.% used previously to 40 vol. %, which is similar to the values used in other
17 additive manufacturing techniques such as robocasting [9,14]. This increment elevated the viscosity of the
18 suspension to levels impractical for the DLP technique. Thus, a 30 wt. % of camphor was added to the resin to
19 reduce the viscosity of the final mixture, emulating previous studies [22]. The selected concentration of
20 camphor was the highest that could be completely dissolved in the resin at room temperature. The viscosity of
21 the resulting slurry after adding the ceramic powder was 1.9 Pa·s (measured at 40 °C and a shear rate of 10 s⁻¹),
22 a value that is within the range reported for a good printability.
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33 SEM micrographs of representative sintered scaffold samples with dense, hollow and hybrid struts fabricated
34 with the optimized suspensions are shown in Figure 4. The shape of the final scaffolds adjusts well to the
35 initial CAD models and the struts appear well defined, with centered internal channels. However, it is evident
36 (Figs. 4d and 4e) that unlike in the 3D-model, the internal channels do not have a perfectly circular shape,
37 being somewhat flattened at the top. This is attributed to residual resin drops that remains hanging from the
38 channel roof after it is built and become exposed to scattered UV light as the rest of the layers are deposited
39 until the channel is finished. The residual resin solidification can be observed, although less markedly due to
40 the flatter geometry, at the bottom surfaces of all struts throughout the scaffold. The surface appearance was
41 noticeably improved with respect to previous studies [29]: it is possible to identify the different building
42 layers in the typical stair step features, but no surface delamination is evident. This is attributed to the
43 increased ceramic content in the suspension, which also played a role in reducing warpage and shrinkage
44 during the sintering process.
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58 The dimensions of the parts after printing differed from the CAD model by less than 10 % and the shrinkage
59 produced during sintering varied from 5 to 10%, being slightly higher along the printing direction. Final
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4 measured dimensions were 1.07 ± 0.03 mm and 0.50 ± 0.01 mm for the external (d) and internal diameter (d_i)
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6 of the struts, respectively, and 1.94 ± 0.03 mm and 1.50 ± 0.02 mm for the horizontal (s) and vertical (h)
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8 center-to-center spacings, which yield pore sizes well within the range of optimal values for enhancing bone
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10 formation [2,4,30].
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14 In the case of hybrid scaffolds (Figs. 4g-i), it is possible to observe the presence of PCL completely filling all
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16 channels after a successful impregnation. Indeed, the impregnation process was greatly facilitated by the
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18 channel interconnections and could be performed flawlessly and reproducibly. Any defects observed in the
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20 cores were produced during sample cutting and the polymeric phase was, as expected, perfectly
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22 interconnected all along the scaffold (see inset in Fig. 4g). However, no clear evidence was found of PCL
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24 penetrating the minor residual microporosity still present on the TCP channel walls to any significant depth.
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26 This indicates that most of the remaining strut microporosity is not open.
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29 Estimated apparent densities were 1.62 ± 0.03 g/cm³ and 1.27 ± 0.02 g/cm³, for specimens with dense and
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31 hollow struts, respectively, corresponding to a total porosity of approximately 47% in dense scaffold that
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33 increases to 59% in the hollow structure due to the contribution of the internal channels. From measured
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35 dimensions in SEM micrographs the macroporosity of the samples, discounting internal channels, was
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37 roughly estimated to be around ~36%. These calculations ignore the rounding at the corners and any other
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39 minor departures from the regular shapes in the original designs but enable us to estimate that the
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41 microporosity within the ceramic walls is of roughly 17 %. Besides, with these estimations, the measured
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43 density in hybrid structures, 1.37 ± 0.02 g/cm³, is compatible with a complete impregnation of the channels,
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45 providing no evidence of any significant reduction in the microporosity within the ceramic walls. While
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47 detrimental to the mechanical performance, the presence of this microporosity and the aforementioned surface
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49 roughness should be beneficial in biological terms, as these two parameters have been shown to favour the
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51 attachment and proliferation of osteoblasts [4,6,31].
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54 Dense-struts scaffolds underwent compression tests in two loading configurations, applying a load either
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56 parallel (\parallel) or perpendicular (\perp) to the printing plane. Figure 5a shows representative stress-strain curves
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58 corresponding to each of them, showing a significantly different response: while specimens loaded in
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60 perpendicular configuration presented multiple local cracking, the ones subjected to parallel loads reached
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4 peak strength without any significant prior fracture event. This is also appreciable on the in-situ images
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6 captured during the tests (Fig. 5b). In the parallel orientation, fractures appear abruptly and run completely
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8 through the sample in the vertical direction and then multiply in number, while when loading is applied
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10 perpendicularly cracking occurs more progressively, with evidence of some transversal fracture. The average
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12 compressive strength (σ_c) is also doubled in the parallel configuration (37 ± 8 MPa vs. 19 ± 4 MPa), although
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14 both values are well above the typical range of cancellous bone (2-12 MPa) [4,32]. As suggested in previous
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16 studies, this strength difference and the distinct fracture modes observed in the scaffolds when submitted to
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18 each load configuration is attributed to the presence of interlayer defects, which leads to a more shear-
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20 dominated fracture when laminated ceramic materials are tested perpendicularly to the lamellae [29,33]. On
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22 the contrary, when tested parallel to the layers, shear stresses become irrelevant, but the crack still propagates
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24 longitudinally, and abruptly, along the weak interlayers.

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26 Since perpendicular loading is the most deleterious configuration, the rest of the scaffolds were tested
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28 perpendicularly to the printing plane. Stress-strain curves of scaffolds with dense, hollow and hybrid struts
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30 tested in this configuration are compared in Figure 6a.

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32 As already discussed for dense-strut specimens, stress-strain curves for hollow and hybrid structures still
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34 present the serrated curves indicative of multiple cracking events. However, while the structure soon suffers a
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36 complete collapse with the load dropping to zero in the case of hollow-strut scaffolds, a stress plateau is
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38 reached in the case of hybrid scaffolds followed, at larger strains, by a stress increase attributed to compaction
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40 of the fractured specimens. The peak stress values reached in the dense structures are clearly higher than those
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42 in hollow and hybrid structures indicating a significantly higher compressive strength. As clearly observed in
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44 the in-situ images of Fig. 6, especially those for hollow structures (Fig. 6b), two main cracking modes are
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46 observed: longitudinal fracture of the rods through their vertical diameter (white arrows) and transversal
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48 fracture of the struts close to the intersections between rods (black arrows). Evidences of the increased
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50 mechanical integrity of the hybrid structure are also obvious in Fig. 6c, with no sign of debris on the bottom
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52 plate at the end of the tests, unlike in the hollow (Fig. 6b) or dense structures (Fig. 5b).

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56 The observed damage modes can be easily justified under the light of the stress fields developed during the
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58 compressive tests. As shown in the FEM calculated contours of Figure 7, maximum tensile stresses in the
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4 interpenetrated structures are located at the intersections of the internal channels (Fig. 7a, white arrows). The
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6 location of the maxima is similar to that in conventional log-pile structures (Fig. 7b). However, while in the
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8 latter the orientation of the stresses at those locations is biaxial, on the interpenetrated structure they are
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10 oriented orthogonal to the strut axis, promoting the longitudinal cracking of the rods. The fact that such
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12 longitudinal fracture was not observed in the log-pile scaffolds [34] despite the biaxial nature of the maxima
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14 indicates that propagation of cracks with that orientation is not preferential. The reason can be the presence of
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16 tensile stresses with axial orientation, leading to transversal fracture, all the way to the external surface of the
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18 rods, where secondary maxima with that orientation are found close to the strut intersections (black arrows,
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20 Fig. 7). Nonetheless, the higher intensity of the stresses favouring a longitudinal cracking in the case of the
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22 interpenetrated structures dominates and this should be considered the primary fracture mode. Although this
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24 does not preclude transversal fracture from occurring at the location of those secondary maxima, as evidenced
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26 in the in situ experimental observations (Fig. 6b).
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30 FEM results in Fig. 7 show also that maximum stresses are substantially higher (by 56 %) in the hollow
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32 interpenetrated structures compared to the log-pile configuration. However, as shown in Fig. 8a, the
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34 experimental average strengths in all-ceramic structures were significantly higher than corresponding
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36 previous results on coaxial hybrid scaffolds with log-pile architecture fabricated also by DLP [34]. The
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38 strengthening of the structure is, thus, completely attributed to the increased solid loading in the DLP resin
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40 suspension used in this study. In any case, although strength is not improved by the new design, the fact that
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42 the polymeric core is three-dimensionally continuous is still considered beneficial in terms of a more isotropic
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44 toughening and mechanical behaviour of the structure. Indeed, with this novel design, polymer fibres exist
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46 along the three cartesian coordinates defining the scaffold network, while in the more conventional log-pile
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48 structures they are only present along two orthogonal directions, leaving the third direction unreinforced.
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50 Moreover, fibres in the new design are all interconnected which should make them more effective against
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52 shear stresses and multiaxial loads. And finally, as already mentioned, the co-continuous design was found to
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54 be beneficial also in terms of facilitating the infiltration procedure.
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57 The compressive strength was significantly reduced in the hollow and hybrid structures compared to the dense
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59 strut specimens—down to just 5 ± 2 and 6 ± 2 MPa from 19 ± 4 MPa, respectively— but were not statistical
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4 different ($p > 0.05$) from each other and remained within cancellous bone range (see shaded bands in Fig. 8).
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6 Therefore, although hybrid struts exhibit a somewhat higher value, no significant influence of the polymer can
7 be perceived in terms of strength. This contrasts with previous results on log-pile coaxial hybrid scaffolds
8 fabricated either by DIW or DLP, where the location of fracture initiation in compression at the internal
9 channel surfaces, enabled the activation of a defect healing mechanism upon polymer impregnation
10 [13,14,34]. The lack of any major strengthening upon polymer infiltration seems to suggest that defect healing
11 is much less effective in the present case. This could be explained by a reduction in the number and size of
12 precursor defects as a consequence of the increased ceramic strut density associated to the increased solid-
13 loading in the DLP feedstock. Indeed, the factor of strengthening achieved by polymeric impregnation has
14 already been proved to decrease with increased densification of the struts [10,35]. This reduced effectiveness
15 of the defect healing mechanism, together with the fact that FEM-calculated stresses in the ceramic shell were
16 found to increase very slightly (by 1.5 %) upon PCL infiltration instead of being slightly reduced (by 10 %) as
17 in the log-pile configuration, may explain the very mild reinforcement in terms of strength observed in the
18 hybrid scaffolds.
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34 On the contrary, the toughness enhancement is evident when comparing hollow and hybrid scaffolds. As
35 shown in Figure 8b, the strain energy density for strains up to 0.4 ($G_{0.4}$) was one order of magnitude higher
36 for the latter (1.2 ± 0.3 vs. 0.11 ± 0.03 MJ·m⁻³), reaching typical values for natural bone [4]. The strain energy
37 density of the structures with dense struts (1.2 ± 0.4 MJ·m⁻³) is similar to that of hybrid scaffolds, but this is
38 just a consequence of their substantially higher strength rather than any actual resistance to crack propagation.
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44 The toughening achieved is similar to that observed in logpile structures although the absolute value is
45 slightly higher in the latter, which is just attributed to their higher strength.
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4 catastrophic brittle fracture in the in-situ images shown in Figures 9b and 9c. And although the same thing
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6 happened to the ceramic shells in the hybrid scaffolds, the PCL cores kept on stretching and bridging the
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8 fractured ceramic together even after large strains (Fig. 9d). This explains why the hybrid scaffolds retained
9
10 significant load bearing capacity long after peak load was reached (Fig. 9a). The fracture was localized at the
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12 points where the longitudinal struts contacted the others and crack initiation occurred at the external surfaces
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14 of the lowermost struts, where maximum stress are located [8], which explains why the peak loads were
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16 practically the same for all scaffolds.

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18 Indeed, as shown in Fig. 10a, there were no significant differences in the average bending strengths among
19
20 the analyzed samples: 9 ± 1 MPa, 7 ± 1 MPa and 8.5 ± 0.9 MPa were measured for scaffolds with dense,
21
22 hollow and hybrid struts, respectively. On the contrary, as already discussed, the performance of hybrid
23
24 scaffolds in terms of toughness was outstanding thanks to the crack bridging produced by the polymeric cores
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26 within the longitudinal struts (Fig. 9d). As clearly displayed in the bar chart of Figure 10b, improvement
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28 achieved over the all-ceramic structures, particularly those with dense struts, under bending was clearly
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30 superior to what was found in compression. Hybrid scaffolds exhibited a strain energy density at 4 mm
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32 displacement (G_4) more than one order of magnitude higher: 60 ± 20 kJ·m⁻³ vs. 1.9 ± 0.5 and 2.3 ± 0.9 kJ·m⁻³
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34 for dense and hollow structures, respectively. The roughly 30-fold increase observed in bending strain energy
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36 density upon polymer impregnation is similar to those obtained in log-pile structures fabricated by
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38 robocasting [14]. However, unlike in that case, the enhancement here is expected to persist also if the samples
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40 were tested with the printing direction aligned in the longitudinal direction of the specimen, since the same
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42 polymeric fibres would hamper crack propagation also in that case. **With this enhancement, the performance**
43
44 **of TCP scaffolds is brought significantly closer to the performance of natural bone (see shaded bands in Fig.**
45
46 **10) under flexural loads.**

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49 All in all, the results of this study demonstrate, once again, the advantages of using polymeric cores for
50
51 improving the toughness of bioceramic scaffolds without affecting the osteoconductivity of their surfaces.
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53 The improvement on the solid loading of the feedstock (to 40 vol. % of β -TCP powder), which was achieved
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55 by lowering the viscosity of the acrylic resin-based slurry through the addition of camphor, significantly
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57 facilitated the debinding and sintering process. A substantial increase in the scaffold strength was also
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59 achieved compared to preceding results, although this enhancement was made less evident due to the change
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4 in the structure design introduced to achieve co-continuous polymeric cores. Although the new design
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6 increases somewhat the stresses developed within the structure in compression, thereby lowering its
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8 compressive strength, it is still deemed beneficial both in terms of facilitating the polymer infiltration and
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10 improving the isotropy of the mechanical enhancement provided by the ductile phase, as already discussed.
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12 Additional improvements in the strength could be achieved by reinforcing the channels at the intersections
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14 where maximum tensile stresses are located, and by optimizing the overall shape of those intersections to
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16 minimize the developed stresses. The high nominal resolution of DLP technique would come handy in this
17
18 future endeavour of achieving an optimal design, where multiaxial toughening could be produced upon
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20 impregnation without negatively affecting the compressive strength of the scaffolds compared to a dense
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22 structure. This would certainly pave the way for obtaining reliable scaffolds for the repair and regeneration of
23
24 bone defects in load-bearing regions of the skeleton.
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27 28 **4. Conclusions** 29

30 The scaffold design with cartesian intersecting struts was proved to be suitable for producing co--continuous
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32 polymer/ceramic hybrid core-shell scaffolds. The design facilitates infiltration of the molten polymer via
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34 suction, and it is expected to provide a more multiaxial reinforcement upon impregnation. The design has still
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36 room for improvements in terms of compressive strength but has been proved to provide significant
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38 toughening, especially in bending. And although this has yet to be evaluated *in vitro* and *in vivo*, core/shell
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40 hybrid scaffolds are expected to biologically outperform coated or totally impregnated hybrid scaffolds, as
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42 they preserve intact the osteoconductive properties of the bioceramic material, as well as the scaffold
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44 macroporosity,
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55 **Acknowledgments** 56

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4 **Figure Captions**
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7 Figure 1. Schematic model of a hybrid core/shell scaffold with interpenetrated struts.
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10 Figure 2. 3D-model of the scaffolds with hollow interpenetrated struts: (a) external view, (b) same with a
11 cross-sectional cut to show the interconnected channels and all feature dimensions, and (c) larger part with
12 infiltration appendages from which each individual scaffold was cut.
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16 Figure 3. Thermogravimetric (TGA) and derivative thermogravimetric (DTG) curves of a green body at a
17 heating rate of 5 °C/min.
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21 Figure 4. SEM micrographs of representative scaffolds with (a-c) dense, (d-f) hollow and (g-i) hybrid struts.
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23 Inset in (g) shows a different cut through the cores' center to show the interconnectivity of the polymer
24 throughout the structure.
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28 Figure 5. Representative (a) stress-strain curves and (b) in-situ optical sequences obtained during uniaxial
29 compression tests on scaffolds with dense struts when loaded in direction either parallel or perpendicular to
30 the printing plane, as indicated.
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34 Figure 6. Plots of (a) representative stress-strain curves and in-situ optical sequences taken during uniaxial
35 compression tests in scaffolds with (b) hollow and (c) hybrid struts. Arrows indicate the location of some
36 longitudinal (white) and transverse (black) cracks.
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41 Figure 7. Stress contours for the maximum principal stress, normalized by applied stress, on the representative
42 central cell of hollow strut scaffolds with a) the interpenetrated design hereby proposed and b) a conventional
43 log-pile architecture. Arrows indicate the orientation of tensile stresses at each local maximum.
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48 Figure 8. Plots of mean (a) compressive strengths and (b) strain energy densities under compression in
49 interpenetrated scaffolds with dense, hollow and hybrid struts, with standard deviations as error bars. Results
50 for analogous scaffolds with a log-pile architecture from a previous work [30] have been included for
51 comparison. Shaded bands indicate the typical range for human bone [4,36,37].
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57 Figure 9. (a) Representative load-displacement curves and (b-d) in-situ optical images taken during 3-points
58 bending tests performed on scaffolds with (b) dense, (c) hollow and (d) hybrid struts.
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Figure 10. Plots of the mean (a) bending strengths and (b) strain energy densities under bending for scaffolds with dense, hollow and hybrid struts. Error bars represent standard deviations - and the shaded band typical values for human bone [4,36,37].

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